

1 **Identification of a pain-type transmission system in humans with Crohn's Disease.**

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7 We studied total transcription using microarray and next-generation sequencing in the blood and the
8 gastrointestinal tract in humans with inflammatory bowel disease and in mice to identify and describe
9 novel features associated with Crohn's Disease in humans. We identified through study of gene
10 expression differences a GI-neuronal transmission system consisting of a migration and invasion
11 component (CXXC factors, spondins) likely associated with small bowel neuroendocrine signaling, a GI
12 motility component encompassing neuropeptides and brain-derived molecules that function in feeding and
13 gastric emptying (cholecystokinin, progastricin, and others) and a somatostatin component that transduces
14 and/or potentiates a pain-like sensation. The neuroendocrine communication system whose existence is
15 made evident through study of component change in patient tissues likely functions in induction of a
16 pain-type sensation in the gastrointestinal tract in humans with Crohn's Disease, vague in nature, difficult
17 to elucidate and whose identity we describe here for the first time.
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